

1 **Kinase and phosphatase inhibition as a signal transduction-centric approach to adjunctive**
2 **chemotherapies for the treatment of gynecologic cancers: TK1.**

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7 Men and women differ in large part resulting from the presence or absence of gynecologic organs
8 including the ovaries, the uterus, the lining of which is known as the endometrium, and the entry to the
9 uterus (womb), the cervix (1), all of which are targets for development of malignancies (2-7); vulvar
10 cancer is less common (8). Cancer, or unrestricted cell division which develops into a tumor after
11 remaining unchecked, evades active cell death and cell cycle control mechanisms, sustaining its survival
12 through growth factor signals (9) which are transduced to the nucleus to activate and repress transcription
13 of genes (10, 11). These signals are transduced between the plasma membrane and the nucleus by the
14 action of kinases and phosphatases, enzymes that utilize conformational changes and a catalytic site to
15 translate a signal from the extracellular environment to a change in gene expression. Catalytic sites are
16 pharmacologically targetable, and small molecule targeting of the appropriate kinase or phosphatase target
17 will disrupt or block this transduction (12, 13). We utilized whole transcriptome technologies (14, 15) to
18 identify and validate kinase and phosphatase targets in gynecologic oncology, including cancer of the
19 cervix. Here we describe a differentially expressed, up-regulated, and catalytically available kinase target
20 in cervical cancer: TK1.

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27 **Keywords:** kinase, phosphatase, signal transduction, gynecologic oncology, therapeutic targets in cancer,
28 chemical biology, systems biology of human cancer.

We utilize genomic and transcriptomic technologies to study the genomic sequences (DNA), the transcriptome (RNA), the proteome (total collection of proteins in the cell) and epigenetic modification (eg., CpG-DNA) of human cancer (16-20). This includes the primary tumor, the source of the transformation - like mutant variants of p53 - cancer subtypes, like adeno and squamous forms of non-small cell lung cancer, metastasis to distant sites, including the lymph nodes, the lungs, the liver, the brain, and bones, and the circulating tumor stem cell, which emerges from the primary tumor, disseminates through the body and establishes a novel entity in a separate organ (21-26).

Our hypothesis and working strategy dictates that in the short-run, disease complications and therapeutic limitations are best managed using identification of therapeutic targets by whole transcriptome differential expression analyses (subtraction analysis), administered in combination with FDA approved broad-spectrum chemotherapeutics like CDK4/6 inhibitors, and in the long-run, will be enhanced and fully complemented by reverse genetic screening strategies (27, 28) to blindly identify disease-specific, subtype-specific and metastasis-specific therapeutic vulnerabilities, fully augmented by novel immunotherapy approaches. Here we describe a kinase therapeutic target identified through rigorous study of the cervical cancer transcriptome: a kinase target that is up-regulated and catalytically available: TK1.

Results

Figure 1: TK1 is differentially expressed in cervical cancer.

I. Primary tumors of the cervix from humans with cervical cancer.

n=5 normal cervical tissue

n=5 primary tumors (cervix; human)

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
202338_at	0.00460847	-3.6136209	-1.8811	-1.864054	TK1	1015/22277	95.4

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the normal cervical tissue and in primary tumors of humans with cervical cancer (14), we discovered differential expression of thymidine kinase 1, encoded by *TK1* in cervical cancer in humans (**Chart 1**). The expression of TK1 changed more than 95% of the human cervical tumor transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 22277 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of TK1 messenger RNA in cervical tumors, demonstrating up-regulation of TK1 during transformation of the cervix.

II. Primary tumors of the cervix from humans with cervical cancer.

n=22 normal cervical tissue

n=20 primary tumors (cervix; human)

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
ILMN_1806037	1.03e-05	-5.02	3.250505	-1.82	TK1	1083/42670	97.5

1 Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the primary tumors of humans with
2 cervical cancer relative to normal cervical tissue, in a second microarray dataset (15) from independent
3 investigators, we validated differential expression of TK1 in cervical cancer in humans (**Chart 2**). The
4 expression of TK1 here changed more than nearly 98% of the human cervical cancer transcriptome when
5 considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 42,670 transcripts (“Rank”).
6 Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of TK1 messenger RNA in cervical tumors,
7 demonstrating up-regulation of TK1 during transformation of the cervix.

8 Thus, differential and increased expression of TK1 defines the transcriptional landscape of cervical
9 cancer in humans.

10 **Discussion**

11 Adjunctive treatments in medical oncology limit the emergence of resistant tumor clones during
12 treatment with a second agent (whether neoadjuvantive chemotherapy or a targeted therapy). Small
13 molecule inhibitors of TK1 kinase, once evaluated for toxicity and safety, can immediately be tested for
14 efficacy in patients with cervical cancer, with the goal of identifying the most effective kinase inhibitors
15 for management of gynecologic malignancies. An approach that combines kinase and phosphatase
16 targeting with a recently described multi-catalytic strategy that targets dNTP synthesis, replication of the
17 daughter strand and activity at the spindle at anaphase, likely delivered in conjunction with standard
18 chemotherapies and drug resistance pump inhibitors in resistant cases, is most likely to be most effective
19 in limiting tumor clone resistance and disease (29).
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Methods

We utilized GSE63678 for this tumor transcriptome study, measuring whole transcription in primary tumors from humans with cervical cancer, as compared to normal cervix (along with GSE67522 for target validation) using microarray data (published) and R-based computational methods (GEO2R).